

OUTSOURCED AND TECHNOLOGY-AIDED INSTRUCTION ON DEMONSTRATION-BASED SKILLS DURING PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The effective use of learning technology in teaching can improve student involvement, help teachers improve their teaching process, and facilitate learning. It also helps both educators and students build the necessary skills that are critically needed to succeed in today's world. They can also make more inclusive learning environments that promote collaboration and it allows the teachers to gather data on student performance. But we cannot deny that during the pandemic, the greatest challenge of the educators is being isolated from the learners because of poor internet connection, no smartphones, no laptop, and no access to the internet at all. Thus, this research project investigated the practice of outsourced technology-aided instruction on demonstration-based skills during the pandemic. A survey questionnaire was distributed to 57 Senior and Junior High School TLE teachers from Zamboanga City. In this study, a quantitative design was preferred. While selecting the participants, purposeful and convenience sampling was used. The findings showed that most of the TLE teachers used YouTube as one of their sources to show the topic in the form of video and at the same time for demonstration video teaching, and it also revealed that they also used the best practices video made by the other teacher. In other words, TLE teachers used the internet as a source to access content, instructional materials, and resources for their teaching. This study is important because it helps to identify and analyze the best practices of using outsourced instruction and technology that is essential in teaching during the pandemic and through this, they can also gain 21st-century technical skills.

Keywords: COVID-19 Pandemic, Outsourced Instruction and Technology, Demonstration-based Skills